

KELI DARAXTIDA BLUME-EMERY-GRIFFITS MODELI UCHUN ASOSIY HOLATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada biz Keli daraxtlarida Blume-Emery-Griffits modelini ko‘rib chiqamiz. BEG modelining bo‘linuvchi Gibbs o‘lchovlarini tavsiflash muammosini ba‘zi algebraik tenglamalarning yechimlarini aniqlash masalasiga keltiramiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: Keli daraxti, Blume-Emery-Griffits modeli, Gibbs o‘lchovi, Translatsion – invariant.

Blume-Emery-Griffits modeli (ko‘pincha “BEG modeli” deb qisqartiriladi) spin-1 modeli bo‘lib, uning turli fizik tizimlarga, jumladan, ko‘p komponentli suyuqliklar, uch komponentli qotishmalar va ${}^3\text{He} - {}^4\text{He}$ aralashmalariga qo‘llanilishi tufayli keng o‘rganilgan. Nazariy jihatdan, BEG modeli Potts modeli uchun holat fazosini renormalizatsiya qilish guruhi (PSGR) tahlilida muhim rol o‘ynaydi. PSGR bosqichlarida Gamiltonian boshqa, kamroq spin o‘zgaruvchilarga ega Gamiltonianga o‘tkaziladi, bu esa panjaradagi asl spinga bog‘liq bo‘lgan klaster bilan bog‘liqdir. Keli daraxtini $\Gamma^k = (V, L)$ ko‘rinishida ifodalaymiz, bu yerda V - tugunlar soni, L - qirralar to‘plami. Ikki tugun x va y eng yaqin qo‘shnilar deyiladi, agar ular orasida L ga tegishli l qirradi mavjud bo‘lsa. Bunday qirrani quyidagicha belgilaymiz: $l = \langle x, y \rangle$.

Agar x dan y ga $\langle x, x_1 \rangle, \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle, \dots \dots \dots, \langle x_{d-1}, y \rangle$ kabi eng yaqin qo‘shnilar juftliklarining ketma – ketligi mavjud bo‘lsa, u holda bu x dan y gacha yo‘l deb ataladi.

Keli daraxtidagi masofa $d(x, y)$ – bu x dan y gacha bo‘lgan eng qisqa yo‘ldagi qirralar soniga teng.

Agar $A \subset V$ bo‘lsa, holda A da spin konfiguratsiyasi σ_A quyidagi kabi aniqlanadi:

$$x \in A \rightarrow \sigma_A(x) \in \Phi = \{-1, 0, 1\}.$$

Barcha konfiguratsiyalar to‘plami quyidagicha aniqlanadi: $\Omega_A = \Phi^A$. Shuningdek, butun daraxt bo‘ylab barcha konfiguratsiyalar to‘plamini quyidagicha belgilaymiz :

$\Omega = \Omega_V$ va $\sigma = \sigma_V$. Bu yerda σ butun daraxt bo‘ylab spin konfiguratsiyasini bildiradi. Nol magnit maydonli BEG modelining formal Gamiltoniani quyidagi ko‘rinishga ega:

$$H(\sigma) = - \sum_{\langle x, y \rangle \in L_n} (\sigma(x)\sigma(y) + a \sigma^2(x)\sigma^2(y) + b(\sigma^2(x) + \sigma^2(y))) \quad (1)$$

Bu yerda $a \in R$ bog‘lanish doimiysi, $b \in R$ esa kristal maydon kuchini ifodalaydi. $\langle x, y \rangle$ esa eng yaqin qo‘shni cho‘qqilarni bildiradi.

Biz $k = 2$ holatni ko‘rib chiqamiz. $U(\sigma_b) \in \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{13}\}$ har qanday σ_b uchun, bu yerda

$$\begin{aligned} U_1(\sigma) &= \frac{1}{2}(-3 - 3y - 6x) & U_2(\sigma) &= \frac{1}{2}(3 - 3y - 6x) & U_3(\sigma) &= \frac{1}{2}(-1 - 3y - 6x) \\ U_4(\sigma) &= \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3y - 6x) & U_5(\sigma) &= \frac{1}{2}(-2 - 2y - 5x) & U_6(\sigma) &= \frac{1}{2}(2 - 2y - 5x) \end{aligned}$$

$$U_7(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2}(-2y - 5x) \quad U_8(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2}(-1 - y - 4x) \quad U_9(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - y - 4x)$$

$$U_{10}(\sigma) = -\frac{3}{2}x \quad U_{11}(\sigma) = -x \quad U_{12}(\sigma) = -\frac{1}{2}x \quad U_{13}(\sigma) = 0$$

Ta'rif: A konfiguratsiya ϕ nisbiy Gamiltonian H ning asosiy (minimal energiyali) holati deyiladi, agar har qanday $b \in M$ uchun $U(\phi_b) = \min\{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{13}\}$ bo'lsa.

Biz quyidagicha belgilaymiz: $C_i = \{\sigma_b : U(\sigma_b) = U_i\}$ va $U_i(J) = U(\sigma_b, J)$ agar $\sigma_b \in C_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, 13$ bo'lsa. Har qanday $i = 1, 2, \dots, 13$ uchun quyidagicha aniqlaymiz: $A_i = J \in R^2, U_i = \min\{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{13}\}$. (2)

Biroz murakkab, ammo to'g'ri hisob kitoblar quyidagilarni ko'rsatadi:

$$A_1 = \{x \leq 0, y \leq -1 - 2x\} \cup \{x \geq 0, y > -1 - x\},$$

$$A_2 = A_4 = A_6 = A_7 = A_8 = A_9 = \{x = 0, y = -1 - x\},$$

$$A_3 = A_5 = \{x \leq 0, y = -1 - x\},$$

$$A_{10} = \{x \geq 0, y \leq -1 - x\},$$

$$A_4 = A_{12} = \{x = 0, y \leq -1\},$$

$$A_{13} = \{x \leq 0, y \leq -1 - 2x\},$$

va $\bigcup_n A_n = R^2$.

Blume-Emery-Griffits modeli uchun Keli daraxtida asosiy holatlar bo'yicha ba'zi holatlar o'rganilgan.

Teorema: Har qanday $C_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, 13$ sinf va har qanday $\sigma_b \in C_i$ cheklangan konfiguratsiya uchun, Keli daraxtidagi ba'zi aperiodik konfiguratsiya ϕ mavjudki, u yerda $\phi_b^0 \in C_i$ bo'ladi va har qanday $b^0 \in M$ va $\phi_b = \sigma_b$ uchun.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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